

Effect of low soil phosphorus and pH on bacterial blight (BB)

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We studied the effect of low available soil P and pH on BB development in IR8 rice. Four soil samples were collected from Bogra, Rangpur, and Gazipur districts of Bangladesh: Magura (11 ppm P and pH 4.4), Madhupur (14 ppm P and pH 5.4), Mawnapathar (15 ppm P and pH 4.3), and Vagnahati (5 ppm P and pH 5.5).

IR8 seedlings were grown in pots on

Effect of low P on BB development. Bangladesh.^a

Soil	Available P (ppm)	pH	BB lesion ^b (%)	SES ^c score
Mawnapathar, Gazipur	15	4.3	30.15 b	7
Vagnahati, Gazipur	5	5.5	14.99 a	5
Magura, Bogra	11	4.4	24.46 b	5
Madhupur, Rangpur	14	5.4	21.65 b	5

^aMeans of 3 replications. ^bFigures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P 0.05 level. ^cStandard evaluation system for rice ratings.

those soils. Plants were fertilized with 100 ppm N from urea and 40 ppm K from muriate of potash, but no P was added. They were inoculated by leaf clipping with a 72-h-old bacterial culture

of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* at maximum tillering.

Lesion length was significantly lowest (15%) 21 d after inoculation in Vagnahati soil (see table). □

Pest Control and Management INSECTS

Elophila sp.? *africalis* Hampson (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae): A new pest of azolla in Sierra Leone

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A research program initiated in 1981 uses azolla as a biofertilizer for rice in associated mangrove and inland valley swamps. Agronomic trials in experiment station and farmers' fields in Sierra Leone and Guinea involve both local and exotic azolla to identify and select strains with competitive biomass production and adaptability.

An outbreak of leaf-feeding insect larvae on *Azolla pinnata* var. *imbricata* strain PI-I37 occurred in late 1985 at Rokupr. Larvae were collected and

Duration of growth stages of *Elophila* sp.? *africalis* Hampson reared on *Azolla pinnata* var. *imbricata* at Rokupr, Sierra Leone, 1985.

Growth stage	Duration (d)		Observations (no.)
	Range	Average	
Egg		4-54.3	25 batches
Larva	18-25	23.1	236
Pupa	4-5	4.6	51
Adult	3-4	3.3	75

reared in the laboratory until adults emerged.

The moth was identified as *Elophila* sp.? *africalis* Hampson by J. D. Bradley of the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, British Museum (National History). This species is reported to have been reared only from *Pistia*.

This is the first time *E. africalis* has been found on azolla in Sierra Leone. Other species in the genus *Elophila* have caused considerable damage to azolla at IRRRI in the Philippines.

In preliminary studies of the

reproductive biology of *E. africalis* in our laboratory at room temperature and 89-92% relative humidity, moths emerging from larvae collected from infested cultures of *A. pinnata* var. *imbricata* were the source of insects. Females deposited eggs, in batches of 16 to 165, on the adaxial side of the floating azolla frond close to the edge. Neonate larvae emerged 4 d later (see table).

Field surveys indicated *E. africalis* has wide distribution in Sierra Leone. □

Leaffolder (LF) population on rice under drought

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An insect population buildup is influenced by weather. During the 1986 wet season, a drought prevailed in most of Madhya Pradesh, with 1 wk cloudy weather and no rain 20 Aug-10 Sep around the Jabalpur district. LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* attacked most

ricefields.

A limited roving survey in Sep noted incidence on dwarf and tall rice varieties in both rainfed and irrigated fields. Leaf damage was moderate in fertilized fields. At the University Nucleus Seed Production Farm, average intensity was 2.0 damaged leaves/hill on short-duration Poorva and 5.8 damaged leaves/hill on medium-duration IR36.

The long dry spell interrupted by cloudy weather may have adversely affected the numbers of natural enemies, promoting LF buildup. □